

Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Drumstick Leaves Powder Supplementation in Prevention of Anemia among Adolescent Girls in Community, Bangalore: An Original Study

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Abstract:

Background: Anemia is leading cause of mortality among adolescent girls worldwide. It is necessary to improve the hemoglobin level for preventing anemia. This study was aimed to assess the effectiveness of DSLP intervention on anemia among adolescent girls with Iron Deficiency Anemia in community, Bangalore. This study was done with the intention of finding an efficient substitute in the form of non-haem iron of vegetable origin in drumstick leaves by administering as supplementation to treat nutritional anemia. Randomized clinical trial design was used in this study, the target group consisted adolescent girls with mild and moderate anemia.

Methods & Materials: The research design selected for this study was true experimental (pre and posttest control group design). The study was conducted in community under Urban Family Welfare Centre, Yeshwantpur, Bangalore. The samples are selected by systemic random sampling technique. Sample size was 60 anemic adolescent girls (10 to 19 years). The instruments used for this study were interview schedule, checklist to identify signs and symptoms of anemia, and Cyanmethemoglobin method to check Hb level, 60 anemic adolescent girls were selected through these instruments and pretest procedure and divided into two groups (Experimental and Control). One teaspoon of DSLP intervention for 30 continuous days was given to the experimental group. At end of the month posttest done for the finding out the effectiveness of DSLP intervention in prevention of anemia among adolescent girls.

Result: Revealed that the Experimental group's pretest mean score of Hb level $10.427(\pm 0.3552)$ and posttest mean scores of Hb level $10.660(\pm 0.2978)$ paired sample t-value 12.042 and DF 29, which is significant at $P < 0.05$ level. It shows the effectiveness of DSLP intervention among adolescent girls with anemia in community, Bangalore.

Interpretation & Conclusion: The study findings revealed that there is a significant difference in the pre and posttest Hb level score with drumstick leaves powder intervention ('t' value 12.042). Therefore, it is evident that the DSLP intervention is effective in reducing iron deficiency anemia among adolescent girls.

Keywords: DSLP- drumstick leaves powder, Hb- Hemoglobin level.

Introduction

Moringa Oleifera or drumstick is native to the sub-Himalayan tracts of India, Pakistan, Bangladesh and Afghanistan where it is used in Folk Medicine (Bender, et al., 1992). It is now widely distributed all over the world (Block, et al., 1988). Moringa Oleifera is referred to as a “Miracle tree” or a “Wonder tree” (Bonnar, Goldberg, & Smith, 1969) of significant socio-economic importance because of its several nutritional pharmacological and industrial applications (Makkar and Becker, 1997; Foidl, 2001). Fuglie (2005) reported that Moringa Oleifera dried leaf powder of serving will satisfy a child with 14% of the protein, 40% of the calcium, 23% of iron and nearly all the vitamin A that a person needs in a day. One 100gm portion of leaves could provide a reproductive woman with over a third of her daily need of calcium and give her important quantities of iron, protein, copper and Sulphur and vitamin-B (Brown, & Tieman, 1986) Effects caused by malnutrition can be particularly associated with the micronutrient’s insufficiency, are zinc and iron deficiency. Both micronutrients play important role in development of the fetus. (Solistyoningslish, 2011). The total number of adolescent populations in world is 1.2 billion out of which around 243 million belongs to India. (UNICEF, 2011). Globally, anemia affects 1.62 billion people, which corresponds to 24.8% of the population. The highest prevalence is in preschool-age children (47.4%), and the lowest prevalence is in men (12.7%). However, the population group with the greatest number of individuals affected are adolescent and pregnant women (41.8%) (CDC, 1989). In women, anemia may become the underlying cause of maternal mortality and perinatal mortality (CDC, 1993). Nearly 50 per cent of women of reproductive age and 26 per cent of men in the age group of 15-59 years are anemic (Chaudhary, & Dhage, 2008). Nine out of ten anemia sufferers live in developing countries, about 2 billion people suffer from anemia and an even larger number of people present iron deficiency. An alarming 600 million people in South-East Asia are suffering from iron deficiency anemia,

predominantly affecting adolescent girls, women of reproductive age and young children. The condition has a prevalence rate of 74 percent among pregnant women in the region ranging from 13.4 percent in Thailand to 87 percent in India. About 74 percent of pregnant women in Bangladesh, 63 percent in Nepal, 58 percent in Sri Lanka and Myanmar, and 51 percent in Indonesia suffer from anemia (Kassebaum, et al., 2014). In studies conducted in developing countries, adolescent anemia as the greatest nutritional problem. In India, 55 % adolescent girls are anemic (Turner, Parsi, & Badireddy, 2023).

Karnataka is known as a prosperous state of India but the status of anemia among young girls and women is alarming. Anemia continues to be a major health problem across India, and according to the National Family Health Survey 2015-16, 44.8 per cent women in the age group of 15-49 years and 60.9 per cent for children (aged 6-59 months) are anemic in Karnataka. Hemoglobin status of tribal children in Karnataka has not been investigated adequately and extensively. Hematological parameters help to understand the normal growth and nutritional status of the children. A cross sectional purposive sampling study was undertaken to determine the prevalence of anemia among 152 Soliga tribal children belonging to 6+ to 10+ years of Mysore district, Karnataka, India. Hemoglobin level was determined by cyanmethemoglobin method. As per the WHO cut-off points, the children were grouped under mild, moderate and severe anemia where the level of hemoglobin below 11.5 g/dL. BMI values were estimated based on the measurements of height and weight of the children. The overall prevalence of anemia was 91.4%; 7.2% mild, 74.3% moderate, and 9.9% severe anemia. Mean hemoglobin values between boys and girls of 7+ years age group were statistically significant. A higher proportion of girls were severely anemic in the age group of 9+ and 10+ years than boys. The prevalence of different grades of anemia was more or less equally distributed among boys and girls of Soliga children. Remarkably, about 94.3%

normal BMI children were anemic. Comparison of mean values of anemia and BMI between boys and girls were found statistically significant. The level of hemoglobin among Soliga Children in Karnataka is a cause for concern. Appropriate measures should be taken by the respective authorities to decrease the prevalence of anemia and improve the condition of health among the children.

A cross sectional survey was conducted in selected anganwadi center of rural area of Hassan district. The conclusion of the survey was a high prevalence of anemia among adolescent girls was found which can higher in low economic strata. It was seen that anemia affect overall nutritional status of adolescent girls. The study was conducted at the faculty of family and community sciences included 100 adolescent girls with mild to moderate anemia the study concluded that drumstick leaves had a major role in the reduction of anemia. Early detection, management, nutrition awareness and dietary modification would reduce the severity of anemia. Various measures are undertaken to compact anemia among population of developing countries, like therapeutic supplementation of iron and folate tablets, fortification of diet with iron and various public health programs thereby creating awareness regarding the benefits of rich sources of iron

Early detection, proper nutrition, awareness and dietary modification would reduce the severity of anemia. Various methods are under taken to compact anemia among population of developing countries like Bangladesh, Myanmar, India, Pakistan, Srilanka, African countries etc. their mean pre-test scores as measured by post-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Methodology

The study was carried out in community under Urban Family Welfare Centre, Yeshwantpur, Bangalore. Randomized clinical trial (one control group one experimental group with pre-test and post-test) design was used. In this study the target group consisted adolescent girls with mild and moderate anemia. 60 (Experimental n=30, Control n=30) adolescent girls with their

hemoglobin level between 9-12 gm/dl were selected as samples. Written consent was obtained from the each individual, along with ethical clearance was obtained from the ethical committee of R.R. College of Nursing and Urban Family Welfare Centre head to conduct the study. The study was conducted over a period of 30 days, from 15th April, 2019 to 15th May, 2019. The purpose of the study was explained to every respondent so as to get their full cooperation. Before intervention hemoglobin level was checked. Adolescent girls with Hb level ranging from 9-12 gm/dl were included in the study. Intervention was started with one tea spoon (5gm) dried drumstick leaves powder supplementation once a day with meals for 30 days. Inhibitors of iron absorption such as tea coffee were withheld along with the dietary supplementation to the experimental group during the intervention. At the end of the study, 30th day 2ml of blood was drawn through vein puncture from both the groups in EDTA tubes. The samples were transported in a portable box to the laboratory within 2 hours and hemoglobin levels were assessed.

Objective

To determine the effectiveness of dry drumstick leaves powder supplementation in prevention of anemia among adolescent girls.

Assumption

- Anemia is more prevalent among adolescent girls because they do not consume adequate diet containing iron rich meals.
- Adolescent girls may have less knowledge about anemia.
- Dietary supplementation of dry drumstick leaves powder can contribute to combat iron deficiency anemia.
- Collection of blood sample for Hb estimation is a therapeutic, aseptic and painful procedure which can cause discomfort to the client.

Delimitations

- The pilot study was delimited to adolescent girl's age between the age group of 10-19 Years.

- Only two samples of blood were collected for pre-test and posttest for estimation of Hb gm/dl.
- Only Cyanmethaemoglobin method was used to estimate Hb level.

Hypothesis

H₀: The mean post-test scores of respondents exposed to “supplementation of drumstick leaves powder in prevention of anemia” will be no difference in their mean pre-test scores as measured by post-test at 0.05 level of significance

H₁: The mean post-test scores of respondents exposed to “supplementation of drumstick leaves powder in prevention of anemia” will be more than

Baseline Data

Baseline data were collected on socioeconomic status, based on clinical symptoms checklist to identify anemia, and laboratory examination for estimation of Hemoglobin level.

Data Analysis

The data collected were coded. Descriptive (Mean, Standard Deviation) and inferential statistics (Independent t test), ANCOVA were used for data analysis.

Results and Discussion

Baseline data, on religious reveal that majority of selected adolescent girls were Hindu (75%) and Muslim (25%). 73% parents of samples were educated and high school passed out. Family income for all the girls were more than Rs.15000 per month. Flow of menstruation found 58% normal, where 47% girls were having history of heavy menstrual flow based upon the number of using sanitation pads during periods. 36% girls were having history of 6 to 8 days duration of menstruation. 41% girls were vegetarian and 58% girls were having history of less than 6 hours of sleeping pattern per day.

Figure 1. The Mean Scores of Pretests and Posttest Hb Level of Anemia among Adolescent Girls of Both Experimental and Control Group

Test	Variables	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t value	DF	P value Inference
Pre test	Experiment	10.427	0.3552	0.24	8.037	58	0.000*
	Control	11.050	0.2330	0.06			
Post test	Experiment	10.660	0.2978				
	Control	10.987	0.2623				

Note: * is significant; ^{NS} is not significant, P<0.001

Table 1. Shows that the mean scores of pretests Hb level of anemia among adolescent girls of both Experimental and Control group 10.427 (SD ±0.3552) gm/dl and 11.050 (SD ±0.2330) gm/dl respectively. Posttest Hb level of anemia among adolescent girls of both Experimental and Control group 10.660 (SD ±0.2978) gm/dl and 10.987 (SD ±0.2623) gm/dl respectively. Thus, the difference in pretest and posttest mean Hb level in Experimental group was 0.24 and in Control group was 0.06. Posttest Hb level of anemia among adolescent girls of Experimental group mean score is more than the Pretest score, was significant at P<0.001 level.

Figure 1. Comparison on Mean Hb Level of Pre and Posttest in Experimental & Control Group

Table 2. Paired Sample t-Test

Groups	Variables	Mean	SD	t value	DF	P value Inference
Experiment n=30	Pre test	10.427	0.3552	12.042	29	0.000*
	Post test	10.660	0.2978			

Note: * is significant; ^{NS} is not significant

Table 2 shows that the Experiment group's pretest mean score of Hb level 10.427(±0.3552) and posttest mean scores of Hb level 10.660 (±0.2978) paired sample t-value 12.042 and Degree of freedom 29, which is significant at P<0.05 level.

Figure 2. Comparison on Mean Hb Level of Experimental Group's Pre and Post Tests

Recommendation and Conclusion

Several recommendations might be made in light of the study's findings regarding the efficacy of supplementing with drumstick leaves powder in avoiding anemia among adolescent females in Bangalore: Health authorities ought to think about using powdered drumstick leaves into current nutrition initiatives aimed at teenage girls. Its high nutritional profile makes it an effective supplement for treating anemia, especially in terms of iron and vitamin c

The study comes to the conclusion that supplementing adolescent females in the Bangalore neighborhood with drumstick leaf powder is a successful strategy for preventing anemia. The participants' considerable increase in hemoglobin levels indicates that adding this natural supplement to their meals can help them make up for any nutritional deficits and achieve better overall health results. Community health programs that encourage the consumption of drumstick leaves can improve young girls' development and well-being while also reducing anemia rates. This strategy is in line with more general public health objectives, such as raising nutritional standards and guaranteeing adolescents' healthy futures. By putting these suggestions into practice, anemia can be considerably decreased and community health can be improved.

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